

TABIIY-ILMIY VA FALSAFIY MUAMMOLARDA INTUISIYA VA SINERGETIKA

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Annotasiya

Maqola hozirgi davr tabiiy-ilmiy va falsafiy muammolarni hal etishda intuisiyaning sinergetik tahliliga bag'ishlangan. Shuningdek, ekologik inqiroz, begonalashuv jarayoni va global inqirozlarni intuitiv hal etish masalasi o'rin olgan.

Kalit so'zlar

bilish, ilmiy bilish, intuitiv bilish, ilmiy tafakkur, begonalashuv jarayoni, ekologik inqirozlar va global inqirozlar.

INTUITION AND SYNERGETICS IN NATURAL-SCIENTIFIC AND PHILOSOPHICAL PROBLEMS

Abstract

The article is deals with to the synergistic analysis of intuition in solving natural-scientific and philosophical problems at present time. Also, the issue of the environmental crisis, the process of alienation and the intuitive solution of global crises has taken place.

Key words

cognition, scientific cognition, intuitive cognition, scientific thinking, alienation process, environmental crises and global crises.

ИНТУИЦИЯ И СИНЕРГЕТИКА В ЕСТЕСТВЕННО-НАУЧНЫХ И ФИЛОСОФСКИХ ПРОБЛЕМАХ

Аннотация

Статья посвящена роли интуиции в решении современных естественнонаучных и философских проблем. Также существует проблема экологического кризиса, процесса отчуждения и интуитивного решения глобальных кризисов.

Ключевые слова

знание, научное знание, интуитивное знание, научное мышление, процесс отчуждения, экологические кризисы и глобальные кризисы.

INTRODUCTION. Today, just as each independent state has chosen its own path of development, independent Uzbekistan is developing on the basis of its own path of development, that is, the concept of evolutionary development. The Uzbek model of development is recognized by the international community due to the fact that it is based on the traditions, values and mentality of the national statehood of our people and at the same time based on the advanced achievements of world experience in reforming society. Also, in today's post-industrial information society of the third wave of civilization, the development of science and science and technology is a determining factor in the development of society, including its material and economic basis, the development of social production. The process of informing the public consists of three interrelated parts: "1) mediation (Latin mediates - mediator) - the process of improving the means of collecting, storing and disseminating information; 2) computerization - the process of improving the means of information retrieval and processing; 3) intellectualization - the process of developing the ability to create and understand information, increase the intellectual potential of society, including the use of artificial intelligence." It is worth noting that an important aspect of informatization is carried out in a combination of technological, social, economic, political and cultural aspects. We also believe that in the current situation, the direction of informatization, its scope and pace depends on the socio-political and cultural processes taking place in society, including science education, the level of globalization of culture. At the same time, globalization is a process that manifests itself in the economic, political, social, cultural, scientific, informational, ideological spheres. In globalization, the strengthening of integration and cooperation between nations and peoples, foreign investment, modern communication and information technologies, the rapid spread of scientific advances, the harmonization of different values on the basis of universal values and increased opportunities for mutual assistance in environmental disasters are positively reflected in globalization. Under the guise of "popular culture" is reflected in the negative aspects of globalization in moral depravity and violence, individualism, egocentrism, environmental disasters, depletion of natural resources, demographic explosions, international terrorism, transnational organized crime and so on.

METHODS: As we know, the German philosopher Oswald Spengler (1880-1936) contrasted the concept of civilization with culture. He noted, "Civilization is a certain final stage of any culture. Its main features are a) industrial and technical development, b) the digitization of literature and art; c) the emergence of large cities with overcrowding; g) the transformation of the people into an imageless

crowd. " However, in our view, while civilization is in a sense a process contrary to the concept of culture, it is inappropriate to completely oppose the concept of civilization to the process of globalization. Only as a whole, the concepts of civilization, culture, globalization can serve society to a certain extent.

The causes of the crises listed above are interpreted as the result of fragmentation. In this case, the first cause of the medical crisis is the separation of body and soul, and the second cause is the treatment of the separation of body parts. In our view, man is a whole organism made up of parts. It reflects not only biological features but also social features. He is a biosocial being. At the same time, in the human mind, we see the harmony of body and soul. Harmony has long been thought of by scientists. In particular, in the philosophy of antiquity, it was argued that the universe consists of a real being only if it is a whole, unchanging.

The diversity of things in the world, their variability, is just an external view of the universe. The Greek philosopher Empedocles believed that the universe was based on four elements – fire, air, water, and earth. Its integrity is the result of the interconnection of these elements. We know that the four elements in the human body depend on the four temperaments in his psyche. Therefore, we come to the conclusion that in the treatment of it, the body and mind must be studied as a whole. Also, in the process of cognition, the problem is solved only in the integrity of rational and irrational thinking, and intuitive thinking plays an important role in this process. Intuition medicine takes a holistic and systematic approach to solving problems.

RESULTS: The first: with a broader analysis of the current state of the globalization process and its impact on the upbringing and thinking of the younger generation, we can say that it can have its positive and negative effects on the human psyche and ideology. In this case, the question of the role of intuition is comprehensive, and intuition forms in the human mind a sense of belonging, integrity, connection to the world. In our view, the positive effects of globalization will be reflected in this process.

The **second**, one of the global crises, the causal consequences of the crisis in medicine are reflected in the fragmentation of the existing order and integrity in them. We know that man is a whole organism made up of parts. It reflects not only biological features but also social features. In man we can see the harmony of body and soul. When the Greek philosopher Empedocles believed that the universe was based on four elements – fire, air, water, and earth – he asserted that its unity and integrity were the result of a combination of these elements. From this point of

view, we come to the conclusion that in medicine it is expedient to study the connection and integrality of body and soul as a whole.

The third, the ecological crisis is a crisis of society, nature and humanity, and it is a violation of the balance between them. At the same time, this process is a growing "alienation." Since man is literally a product of nature and society, he is a part of both nature and society. From this point of view, we believe that it is expedient for man to live in harmony with society and nature, to use nature wisely.

The fourth, the anthropological crisis appears to be the cause of the above crises. It also includes the demographic crisis, the moral crisis, the crisis of values, the crisis of the family, the spiritual crisis, the crisis of education. In our view, the solution of crises is reflected in the combination of rational and irrational thinking in human thinking, based on integrity.

The fifth, economic, political, and social crises are observed within global crises. The economic, political, social and spiritual spheres of society are closely intertwined, and these spheres are its pillars. Of these, the sphere of spiritual life of society firmly connects other spheres and determines the development of society. Hence, we conclude that the prevention and resolution of existing global crises is determined by the raising of spirituality and forms of social consciousness in young people.

DISCUSSION: Firstly, matter and consciousness, the material and spiritual world, the unity of body and soul - it can be assumed that they exist. Also, each of them is inextricably linked to each other. This connection proves the objectivity of all things and events in reality. This unity is also reflected in the category of beings.

The unity of being and its attributes, i.e., objective and subjective being, consists of the unity of action, space, and time. The basic attributes of being are in the unity of materiality and spirituality, in the unity of objective and subjective being; manifested in the unity of matter, motion, energy, power, and information. This principle is confirmed by the development of modern natural sciences, the

theoretical conclusions of classical physics and relativistic physics, the basic postulates, theorems of Euclidean geometry and non-Euclidean geometry, the basic laws of Newtonian physics, the postulates of relativity, the gravitational equations of relativistic cosmology.

a) subsistence: b) movement: c) space: d) time

The problem is the unity of action and its various forms. Different forms of movement: mechanical, physical, chemical, biological, geological, social forms reflect the variability and unity of stagnation, stillness and process. The category of action, which encompasses all changes in the universe, confirms the unity of all forms of action. Their peculiarities express the driving forces of these forms.

The unity of the fundamental forces underlying the universe. Fundamental forces on the basis of the material universe that make up the universe: strong nuclear interaction force (this force consists of the unit of elementary particles that make up the atomic nucleus), electromagnetic interaction force (this force consists of the unit of electrically charged particles, molecular compounds), gravitational interaction force power consists of the structural integrity of the entire Universe). These forces are at the same time the unity of the microworld, the macroworld, and the mega world, and it constitutes the integrity of the universe.

In matter and antimodel, the unity of particles and antiparticles, the mutual equilibrium of particles and antiparticles in the universe, as much as there are particles in nature, there is also its antipode - antiparticles. First, the antipode of the electron - a positively charged positron - was discovered, then the antiparticles of protons and neutrons, antiproton and antineutrons, were discovered. These particles complement each other and form a base for each other. Being in the universe manifests itself not only in the form of matter, but also in the form of space and radiation. They actually have the same fundamental basis. The item or field depends on which accounting system it is viewed from. The presence of a field from one accounting system as a substance, and vice versa, an object as a field becomes a material object in another accounting system. Radiation and field are

also different manifestations of the same thing. The force that unites them is the fundamental forces of the universe. The unity of matter and space, particles and antiparticles ensures the integrity of the universe, the stability of the universe, the material and immaterial world.

The unity of the levels of the scale structure of the material world. It is the unity of the microworld, the macroworld, and the mega world, and their unity and interchangeability is determined by the relativity of the structure of space-time, the unity of fundamental forces, the theory of a single field.

The unity of the levels of the organizational structure of the universe. The organizational structure of the universe is diverse. Inanimate nature differs from animate nature, and animate nature differs from society in its level of activity and organizational structure. They complement each other, they demand each other. The lower level features are also reflected in the higher level structure. The unity of these levels is the unity of the inorganic, organic, and social worlds, which are united by forms of action.

The unity of the information space of the universe. Anything and event in the universe has energy and information power. Energy is stored, transformed from one species to another, manifested in different manifestations. Also, any information is stored, transmitted from one object to another. There is a law of conservation of energy and information, as well as the transformation from one species to another. This existence is a manifestation of the integrity of energy and information, realized in the unity of field information and energy types.

The unity of man and nature (the universe). It manifests itself in the form of the unity of the subject (man) and the object (external world), representing that the subject cannot exist without the object and the object without the subject. Their unity is manifested in the integrity, continuity, and diversity of being. In our view, the unity of the universe should not be one-sidedly absolute. It is also complex and has infinite variety. Modern science is constantly confronted with such diversity. One of the main tasks of the existing natural and social sciences is to prove and substantiate the unity, integrity and diversity of the universe.

Based on the above considerations, we can draw the following conclusions instead of intuition in solving natural scientific and social problems:

CONCLUSIONS: In our view, the process of globalization affects the human mind in the form of information, it penetrates into various spheres of society and begins to show its negative, positive impact, while globalization is manifested in information and ideological processes, which primarily affect its spiritual sphere. Our president Sh. Mirziyoyev used the concept of "spiritual aggression" in his

speeches. "Where indifference and indifference prevail, spirituality becomes the weakest point. Conversely, where vigilance and zeal, high intellect and contemplation prevail, spirituality becomes a powerful force." It should also be noted that moral threats affect them in the form of information attacks. Especially today, in the international arena, the work of various political forces under the guise of promoting "Freedom and Democracy" to achieve their strategic plans is a clear example of this. Before we have a clear understanding of the spiritual threat, we need to focus on the concept of spirituality. "Spirituality is an incomparable force that calls a person to spiritual purification, to the growth of the soul, to the inner world of man, to the strength of the will, to the wholeness of faith, to the awakening of the conscience, the criterion of all his views. Spirituality is a concept that represents the spiritual and mental world of man. "So we believe that the spiritual threat is a process that affects both the mind and the psyche of a person at the same time. In this regard, President SH .Mirziyoyev said, "In order to create a gap in the spiritual world of our youth, we need to instill in their hearts and minds a healthy lifestyle, respect for national and universal values from childhood. At a time when profound changes are taking place in the geopolitical, economic and social, information and communication landscape of the world, and the conflict of different ideologies is intensifying, the struggle against anti-idea, anti-idea, anti-ignorance is more important than ever." they say.

Given the urgency of the matter, we will consider the importance of intuition in this regard. "The global crisis is causing global sectoral crises like itself; medical crises, environmental crises, anthropological crises, demographic crises, resource crises, economic and financial crises, political crises, social crises, moral crises, value crises, spiritual crises, educational crises, global historical crisis. In our view, these crises are mutually exclusive processes with the same causes of formation.

The ecological crisis is interpreted as a disturbance of the balance between nature and society. In our view, this crisis is a clear manifestation of the "alienation process" in the eyes of existentialists. According to existentialists, "The first manifestation of the process of alienation is the alienation of society from nature through the creation of artificial nature; the second stage is the alienation of man from society; the third stage is the self-alienation of man." The French writer and philosopher Albert Camus (1913-1960) elaborates on the state of spontaneous alienation in his book *The Alien*.

In retrospect, in both of the above crises, we observe the state of fragmentation of the whole. In our view, man is literally a product of nature and society, he is a part of the universe. In this sense, it can be said that the ecological crisis is a crisis of

society, nature and humanity. It is obvious that the solution of the crisis is a process that reflects the whole, that is, nature - society - is reflected in the unity and integrity of humanity.

Anthropological crisis is manifested as the cause of the above crises. It includes the demographic crisis, the moral crisis, the crisis of values, the crisis of the family, the spiritual crisis, the crisis of education. In fact, all crises occur because of human thinking and future unintentional behavior. In our interpretation, another important cause of crises is the rational thinking of those who think and act today and follow the rules of existing law. They approach the environment, society and themselves only in terms of material benefits, based on one-sidedness. This creates a ruthless feeling in a person that does not turn away from anything in the way of his own interests and goals. At the same time, a one-sided approach leads to the fragmentation of the whole and its disintegration. Therefore, the representatives of irrational thinking prioritize the situations related to the human psyche, and thus they, too, are based only on one-sidedness. We know that "religion" is a powerful tool that can directly affect the human mind and heart. It is no secret, however, that those who hate religion skillfully can have a negative effect on the integrity of society. In our interpretation, human thinking can find a solution to any problem it may encounter only when it is based on rational and irrational integrity.

Among the global crises, we can observe economic, political and social crises. As a society operates as a whole system, every event and process that takes place in it belongs to a certain sphere of life of the society and at the same time it affects other spheres of the society. It should be noted that the economic, political, social and spiritual spheres of society are closely intertwined, and these spheres are its pillars. It is its spiritual sphere that strongly connects these spheres and determines the development of society. After all, the development of any state or society is reflected in high spirituality. So, we believe that one of the urgent issues is to raise the morale and forms of social consciousness in today's youth in order to prevent the existing global crises and find solutions to them. In spirituality, scientific thinking, intuitive thinking is important.

We talked about integrity, unity in the ideas above. In general, we consider the manifestation of integrity in the occurrence of things and events in the objective world in the following ways:

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